

growth were less in the plots that received ammonium sulfate than in the plots that received urea. Ammonium sulfate also helped decompose weeds. Urea applied a week after crop plowing did not

influence weed decomposition, so most of the weeds re-established. Grain yields were also remarkably increased. Average grain yield was 3.26 t/ha for the ammonium sulfate treatment, and

2.4 t/ha for urea. Since no additional input costs are involved, extension agencies may consider suggesting the method to farmers. ■

Influence of soil moisture regime on iron and manganese release in soil and on the growth of upland rice

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A pot experiment, conducted on Vertic Ustropepts (medium black clay: pH 8.5; CaCO₃, 6.0%; and organic carbon, 0.5%)

in the 1977 rainy season, studied the influence of soil saturation and submergence for 10 and 20 days before sowing on the supply of iron and manganese in the soil and on the dry matter yield of upland rice. The variety used was Karjat 184.

The iron and manganese supply in the soil increased with the duration of soil saturation or submergence (see table). The increase may have been caused by

moderately reduced soil conditions that resulted from soil saturation or submergence before sowing (Eh values decreased from 501 mV to 369 mV and pH decreased from 8.6 to 7.6). Iron and manganese contents in the soil were higher after submergence for 10 or 20 days than after soil saturation. The dry-matter yield increased — probably because of the higher supply of iron and manganese. ■

Iron and manganese contents in soil and dry matter yield of rice as influenced by soil moisture regimes before sowing. Mean of 5 replications. Maharashtra, India

Soil water treatment before sowing	Iron content (ppm)		Manganese content (ppm)		Dry matter yield of rice at harvest (g/5 plants per pot)
	Initial (immediately after soil water treatment)	Final (at the end of soil water treatment period 10 or 20 days)	Initial (immediately after soil water treatment)	Final (at the end of soil water treatment period)	
Soil saturation, 10 days	2.4	2.6	0.7	1.0	5.3
Soil submergence, 10 days	2.6	3.2	0.7	1.3	7.6
Soil saturation, 20 days	2.4	3.6	0.7	1.2	7.5
Soil submergence, 20 days	2.6	4.1	0.7	2.1	8.9
Control (dry soil)	1.2	1.2	0.7	0.7	5.2

A simple test for available zinc and copper in wetland rice soils

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Zinc deficiency is a widespread nutritional disorder of wetland rice. It occurs on alkali, calcareous, poorly drained mineral, and peat soils. Copper deficiency limits rice yields on peat soils and also, perhaps, on other zinc-deficient soils. The need for simple, rapid, and reliable method for estimating zinc and copper in soils used for wetland rice is pressing.

Because the widely used DTPA and EDTA methods consume too much time and chemicals, 0.1 N HCl and 0.05 N HCl as extractants for available zinc and copper were compared with DTPA and

EDTA in a laboratory and greenhouse study of 32 soils covering a wide range of pH and organic matter content.

The 0.1 N HCl method consisted of shaking 2 g air-dry soil with 20 ml 0.1 N HCl for 5 minutes. The 0.05 N HCl method used 10 g air-dry soil, 20 ml 0.05 N HCl, and 5 minutes shaking. The extracts were filtered and zinc and copper determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry, along with the DTPA and EDTA extracts obtained by shaking for 2 hours and 30 minutes, respectively. Rice plants grown on the flooded soils were wet-ashed and the concentrations of zinc and copper measured.

The 0.05 N HCl method gave the best correlation between extractable zinc and copper and their concentration in the plant:

Method	Concn of element in extract vs concn in plant	
	Zn	Cu
ESDTA-(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃	.43**	.28ns
DTPA/TEA	.31 ns	.20ns
0.1 N HCl	.55**	.64**
0.05 N HCl	.88**	.74**

On 13 of the 16 soils that contained less than 1 ppm Zn extractable with 0.05 N HCl, plants showed zinc deficiency symptoms or contained < 27 ppm zinc. Although no copper deficiency symptoms were recognized, plants growing on 13 of 15 soils with < 0.1 ppm Cu by the 0.05 N HCl method contained < 5 ppm copper.

Available zinc (0.05 N HCl) correlated highly with available copper (0.05 N HCl) with $r = .58^{**}$. So did plant zinc and

copper, with $r = .52^{**}$. Apparently, because of similarities in their chemical behavior, copper deficiency may occur in

zinc-deficient soils.

The 0.05 N HCl extraction appears to be an accurate, simple, rapid, and

inexpensive method of measuring available zinc and copper in soils used for wetland rice. ■

Summer plowing overcomes zinc deficiency

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The problem of zinc deficiency (khaira) with high yielding rice varieties is widespread in Allahabad district, India. Applications of farmyard manure and of zinc sulfate are commonly used to

overcome the problem. Farmers have also noted beneficial effects from summer plowing.

During 1977-78 kharif rice plots were selected and observed in national demonstrations and in farmers' fields. The plots that were plowed in summer had no severe deficiency problems even when planted to high yielding, semidwarf rice varieties. Some demonstration plots without summer plowing showed severe zinc deficiency even when supplied with

40 kg ZnSO₄/ha as a basal dressing. They needed a topdressing of an equal amount of ZnSO₄ to overcome the problem.

In a few demonstration plots that were plowed in summer and received 40 kg ZnSO₄/ha as a basal dressing, plants showed no traces of zinc deficiency. Rice plants grown in the plots that were plowed in summer had profuse and deep roots, regardless of other treatments. Presumably the increased root growth helped the plants escape zinc deficiency. ■

Scanning electron micrographs of rice primordia

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The primordia of only a relatively few species of crop plants have been studied in detail. The Division of Land Use Research has a project, nearing completion, to produce a photographic atlas illustrating generally acceptable definitions of floral initiation for the major field crops. The atlas will set standards for agronomists and other scientists studying the development of field crops.

Floral initiation is defined as the first structural change in the apex. In rice the change from the vegetative to the reproductive stage is marked by the initiation of microscopic bracts on the main culm (Photo 2). Panicle development continues and the young panicle primordium eventually becomes visible to the naked eye as a hyaline structure 1-2 mm long with a white fuzzed tip (Photo 4).

Panicle initiation in the field is commonly identified by the appearance of the white fuzzed structure. At temperatures ranging from 25 to 35°C, this stage occurs about 2-3 days after first bract initiation. At lower temperature it occurs much later. The photographs show that the primary

1. Vegetative apex (x75)

2. Several bracts initiated (x75)

3. Bract hairs developing (x75)

4. Approximately 1 mm long and visible as a white fuzzed tip (x25)

branches differentiated before the white fuzzed tip became visible to the naked

eye. The yield potential is therefore largely determined by this stage. ■